

1 **Coseismic reorientation of the crustal stress field at the**
2 **base of the 2019 Ridgecrest earthquake fault zone**

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7 Abstract

8 The evolution of stress and material damage in fault zones is a key control on the seismic cycle and is a crucial link between long-term loading and healing processes and short-term dynamic ruptures. Typical methodologies to monitor changes in stress state and material properties are limited in visibility to the shallow subsurface. Here we explore deep changes in seismic velocity as measured by receiver functions to show that large earthquakes generate large and long-lasting perturbations to the surrounding medium at seismogenic depth. We map this deep seismic velocity change to a localized region around the fault, and show that it is associated with a coseismic rotation in seismic anisotropy. While shallow velocity changes recover within several months, the observed deep seismic velocity changes persist over time without recovery. We propose that our results capture for the first time the coseismic stress effects in the near-fault environment, characterized by a slower recovery timescale, rotation in seismic anisotropy, and localization near the fault. This new sensitivity to the evolving stress state at depth offers a valuable tool for monitoring stress and damage evolution in fault zones, which is essential for a deeper understanding of the coupling between fault mechanics and crustal stresses.

23 1 Introduction

24 Large earthquakes play a key role in plate tectonics by accommodating plate motion, occurring once a fault reaches frictional failure following long-term buildup of crustal stresses. The stress state of any given fault is driven by far-field tectonic forces, but its local distribution along the fault reflects both local structure and the past stressing history due to prior ruptures (Chen et al., 2024). This local structure is not static and is impacted by earthquake ruptures, as evinced by near-fault fracturing at the surface (Rodríguez Padilla et al., 2022) and transient decreases in seismic velocities that likely reflect damage in the shallow subsurface (Brennguier et al., 2008). While earthquakes are the most dramatic phase of the seismic cycle with fast dynamics that dominate the co-seismic rupture, the slow dynamics of the post- and inter-seismic phases also affect the crust surrounding faults, whether it be through afterslip (Qiu et al., 2020), the healing of rock damage (Brennguier et al., 2008), or long-term stress accumulation (Fialko, 2021). Our mechanical understanding of earthquakes requires not just an understanding of dynamic fault rupture, but also the slower processes that set the scene and stress state for the next seismic rupture.

38 Information about stress evolution in fault zones at depth can be determined from the source properties of microseismicity (Allmann & Shearer, 2007; S. Sheng & Meng, 2020). Information about rock damage and healing at depth can be determined from traveltimes variations of microseismicity (Vidale & Li, 2003). In some circumstances, even stress changes can be related to changes in seismic velocities (Niu et al., 2008). These event-based measurements often require special repeating events, and provide information only episodically, often lacking resolution during key phases of the seismic cycle. Noise-based measurements enable continuous monitoring of seismic velocities in the fault zone, but are sensitive primarily to changes in the shallow subsurface (Wu et al., 2016; Yuan et al., 2021). Shallow velocity changes primarily capture the brittle rheology of the near surface materials (Brennguier et al., 2008) and nonlinear elastic stress-sensitivity of the fractures (Y. Sheng, Brennguier, et al., 2024). However, seismic rupture and postseismic deformation span large portions of the crust with different rheological behavior, so to what extent do shallow velocity changes reflect deeper fault zone stress and damage evolution?

53 The 2019 Ridgecrest earthquake doublet, a seismic sequence of a $M_w = 6.4$ event followed by a $M_w = 7.1$ earthquake two days (Ross et al., 2019; Shelly, 2020), provides an ideal case study to explore the evolution of crustal stresses before and after a pair of major seismic ruptures. Previous seismic monitoring studies have demonstrated a large co-seismic velocity reduction in the vicinity of the fault using local seismicity (Lu & Ben-

Zion, 2021) and noise-based techniques (Boschelli et al., 2021; Clements & Denolle, 2023; Y. Sheng, Mordret, et al., 2024). These techniques, most sensitive to changes in seismic structure in the shallow subsurface (<10 km), show a substantial coseismic velocity reduction that fully recovers within several months (Lu & Ben-Zion, 2021; Boschelli et al., 2021). To probe how the roots of a fault zone evolve through a major earthquake sequence, we utilize receiver functions to explore deep changes in seismic velocity structure beneath the 2019 Ridgecrest sequence.

Receiver functions are a form of event-based seismic interferometry that use large ($M_w > 5.0$) earthquakes at teleseismic ($30^\circ - 100^\circ$) distances to map the velocity discontinuities beneath a single three-component seismic station (Phinney, 1964; Bath & Stefánsson, 1966; Burdick & Langston, 1977; Vinnik, 1977; Langston, 1979). As an incident P-wave from a distant earthquake arrives at the base of the crust, it converts some energy into S-waves. Since the direct P- and converted S-waves derive from the same incident P-wave, they carry the same far-field path and earthquake source information. Deconvolution of the *P*-wave recording from the *S*-wave recordings then isolates the post-conversion waveforms resulting from the velocity structure directly beneath the seismic receiver. With ≈ 1500 $M_w > 5.0$ events annually, receiver functions quasicontinuously illuminate the velocity structure of the Earth’s crust wherever there is a broadband seismic instrument. Because teleseismic body waves must propagate vertically through the crust, receiver function are uniformly sensitive to velocity changes at any depth in the crust (Bryan et al., 2023). Additionally, because only a single station is needed to calculate a receiver function, no specific array geometries are needed to capture the velocity change. We leverage these features of the receiver function for time-lapse seismic monitoring of the deep crust.

Seismic monitoring via any technique consists of three fundamental steps: (1) repeated sampling of a source-receiver path, producing an ensemble of nearly identical waveforms, (2) measurement of small time-amplitude signal variations between the repeated waveforms, and (3) interpretation of these variations for their causative seismic velocity change. Challenges in each of these steps have limited the utility of receiver functions for seismic monitoring. First, teleseismic earthquakes have different earthquake sources and travel paths. Receiver functions reduce this variability by removing source and far-field path effects, but variations in the incidence angle and backazimuth of the wavefront confound changes in seismic velocity, making it challenging to isolate the contribution of the latter. Second, velocity changes in the subsurface induce complicated time-amplitude waveform variations in the receiver function. Given an incident P-wave, each arrival in a receiver function corresponds to a P-to-S conversion, so waveform variations can be due to both time shifts accumulated through a velocity perturbation (Audet, 2010; Kim & Lekić, 2019; Richter, 2014) and modified scattering properties at a layer boundary (Gosselin et al., 2020). P- and S-waves may experience different velocity changes, resulting in nonlinear changes to the receiver function (Bryan et al., 2023). Finally, observed phases are generally direct conversions and early reverberations. Their ray paths through a velocity perturbation are shorter than the multiply scattered coda waves used in ambient noise monitoring, so they accumulate smaller travel-time variations. This limits analyses to relatively large velocity perturbations, but this requirement is satisfied by the context this study: a major earthquake sequence within a well-defined fault zone (Lu & Ben-Zion, 2021).

We propose to overcome these challenges through a novel monitoring approach that leverages optimal transport (Bryan et al., 2023). Optimal transport is a mathematical tool for measuring the distance between two distributions by finding a transformation (a “transport plan”) that minimizes the “work” needed to transform a reference distribution into a perturbed observed distribution. This generalized quantitative comparison can capture the nonlinear time-amplitude variations as a function of lag-time of the receiver function waveforms (Bryan et al., 2023). Classic comparative metrics like the

111 L2-norm only quantify the difference in amplitude, while typical monitoring tools like
 112 trace stretching or moving-window cross spectrum only capture changes in time. By per-
 113 forming this analysis in a moving time window, we can monitor the subtle changes in
 114 receiver function waveforms that reflect seismic velocity changes throughout the crustal
 115 column. We also make use of the rich geometric mathematical structure imbued by the
 116 optimal transport distance to perform blind source separation in the space of waveform
 117 variations, allowing us to disentangle velocity changes from path variations (Wang et al.,
 118 2013; Kolouri et al., 2017; Bryan et al., 2023).

119 We build on previous studies by examining seismic velocity changes with receiver
 120 functions. We calculate receiver functions for 31 permanent three-component broadband
 121 seismic stations within ≈ 120 km of the Ridgecrest fault zone (Fig. 1a). Of the 15,678
 122 events with magnitudes greater than 5.0 between 2015 and 2023, we selected $\approx 5,500$
 123 events that met source location and quality control criteria. These receiver functions were
 124 then used to characterize the velocity structure of the crustal column across the fault
 125 zone. We isolate the signature of seismic velocity changes using blind source separation
 126 with optimal transport embeddings, effectively filtering out nuisance variations related
 127 to source backazimuth and incidence angle. This resulted in a time-series of seismic ve-
 128 locity changes across the fault zone with a 30-day time resolution. We use synthetic re-
 129 ceiver function modeling to demonstrate that both deep and shallow velocity changes
 130 respond coseismically; however, their evolution then decouples with the shallow changes
 131 fully recovering while the deeper changes remain perturbed over longer timescales. To
 132 explore the physical mechanisms this deep, persistent velocity change, we reintroduce
 133 the backazimuth dependence of the receiver functions to estimate a time series of seis-
 134 mic anisotropy. Our findings reveal a coherent coseismic rotation of the fast-axes of seis-
 135 mic anisotropy across the fault zone, indicating that variations in fault zone stress can
 136 be effectively monitored through passive seismic observations.

137 2 Deep seismic velocity changes.

138 Receiver functions before and after the Ridgecrest earthquake show distinct dif-
 139 ferences, including changes in amplitude as well as clear time delays following the earth-
 140 quake (Fig. 1c), with considerable amplitude variation from sample to sample attributable
 141 to a combination of noise variation and path variation. To investigate these changes, we
 142 first define a reference receiver function by stacking the receiver functions from January
 143 1, 2015 - July 4, 2018 (one year prior to the Ridgecrest earthquakes). We then calculate
 144 the optimal transport map from each individual receiver function to this reference re-
 145 ceiver function, capturing the nonlinear time-amplitude signal variations characteristic
 146 of both velocity changes and teleseismic source variation (Bryan et al., 2023). We use
 147 these optimal transport maps and their associated distances to perform a linear optimal
 148 transport embedding on each waveform, which renders the complex time-amplitude wave-
 149 form variations into simple Euclidean perturbations (Wang et al., 2013; Kolouri et al.,
 150 2016). We retain the first 50 principal components in this embedding space and then sep-
 151 arate the variation into 10 independent components. This approach successfully isolated
 152 the velocity change onto specific components, with residual variations accounting for back-
 153 azimuth variability and other waveform differences. To reconstruct the time-domain re-
 154 ceiver functions cleaned of backazimuth and incidence-angle variation, we average the
 155 embeddings in a thirty-day moving window with a 1-day step and perform the inverse
 156 transformation from our linear embedding space (Fig. 2a). We then calculate the lag-
 157 time dependent optimal transport distance (Fig. 2c) and map the coseismic perturba-
 158 tion in optimal transport distance across the fault zone (Fig. 1a-b).

159 The absence of a significant perturbation in the optimal transport distances on July
 160 4, 2018 confirms that the reference receiver function does not introduce artifacts into the
 161 time series. The optimal transport distances remain stable over time prior to the 2019
 162 Ridgecrest earthquakes, but show a clear coseismic velocity reduction at the time of the

163 earthquake (Fig. 2c). Immediately following the event, waveform changes associated with
 164 early lag-times (0.0-2.5 sec), which capture direct converted phases and shallow rever-
 165 berations, were more pronounced than those associated with later lag-times (7.5-10.0 sec),
 166 which capture deeper reverberations. The early lag-time perturbations decay more rapidly
 167 than the later ones, though both show a permanent perturbation that does not fully re-
 168 cover. In contrast, ambient noise autocorrelations, another single-station method with
 169 shallower depth sensitivity, show complete recovery within several months, consistent with
 170 past ambient noise results in the region (Boschelli et al., 2021) and other methods with
 171 shallow depth sensitivity (Lu & Ben-Zion, 2021). This discrepancy suggests that deeper
 172 velocity changes, only detectable with methods probing deeper fault zone structures, de-
 173 couple from the healing of the shallow velocity change (Y. Sheng, Mordret, et al., 2024).

174 Given the observed differences in the evolution of shallow and deep velocity changes,
 175 we now investigate the depth at which these changes occur and how they relate to the
 176 earthquake rupture. To do this, we consider the relationship between the lag-time of phases
 177 in the receiver function and the depth at which these phases originate. The lag-time cor-
 178 responds to the differential arrival time between each phase and the direct P-wave, with
 179 longer S-P times indicating greater conversion depths. Alternatively, greater lag-times
 180 correspond to reverberated phases. To accurately estimate the depth of the velocity change,
 181 and to differentiate between deep velocity changes and shallow reverberated phases, we
 182 invert the receiver functions for a layered velocity model and examine the effect of syn-
 183 thetic perturbations on each part of the waveform. Although the detailed structure of
 184 this model is not the primary focus here, it is essential for associating specific lag-times
 185 with the corresponding depths of direct and reverberated phases.

186 We perform an ensemble of gradient-based inversions for a layered velocity model,
 187 using the high resolution seismic imaging in the area to define an set of high quality ini-
 188 tial models (White et al., 2021). We then varied the number of layers and selected a model
 189 with 25 layers by minimizing the Akaike Information Criterion . To explore how veloc-
 190 ity changes at different depths affect the waveform, we simulated synthetic receiver func-
 191 tions using this layered velocity model with Telewavesim (Audet et al., 2019). By ap-
 192 plying a 1% V_s perturbation to various layers within the model, we calculated the op-
 193 timal transport distance between the reference and perturbed receiver functions (Yuan
 194 et al., 2021). As we varied the depth of the perturbed layer, we observed that velocity
 195 perturbations induce strong waveform changes characterized by two distinct moveouts
 196 (Fig. 2b). The first moveout, associated with direct converted phases, is particularly promi-
 197 nent for crustal phase conversions occurring above 25 km depth, impacting waveform per-
 198 turbations up to 2.5 seconds. Perturbations in the waveform observed between 7.5-10.0
 199 seconds cannot be explained by perturbation of direct crustal conversions and must be
 200 reverberated phases. The question, then, is at what depth were these reverberated phases
 201 generated and what is their travel path? We see that shallow velocity perturbations can
 202 generate waveform perturbations out to ≈ 6.0 seconds through high order reverbera-
 203 tions, but they rapidly lose energy with increasing reverberation order. Thus, the per-
 204 turbations in the waveform observed between 7.5-10.0 seconds cannot be explained by
 205 shallow layers alone, and likely result from reverberated phases originating at depths of
 206 10-20 km.

207 This suggests that a deeper velocity change is present alongside the shallow veloc-
 208 ity change imaged by ambient noise (Boschelli et al., 2021) and local seismicity (Lu &
 209 Ben-Zion, 2021), and hinted at by methods with greater depth sensitivity (Y. Sheng, Mor-
 210 dret, et al., 2024). By measuring the velocity change with two single-station techniques
 211 with identical processing, at many stations across the fault zone, we conclude that this
 212 is a deep velocity change rather than a spatially heterogeneous velocity change at some
 213 distance away (Fig. 1a-b). The early lag-times in the receiver function are initially more
 214 perturbed than the later lag times because they are sensitive to both the deep and the
 215 shallow velocity changes, sampling the substantial shallow velocity change several times

216 via shallow reverberations. As the shallow velocity change recovers, the early lag-times
 217 recover almost to pre-earthquake levels, but remain perturbed due to their sensitivity
 218 to the deep velocity change through direct converted phases. The later lag-times, on the
 219 other hand, remain substantially perturbed due to repeated sampling of the deep velocity
 220 change through reverberations (Fig. 2c).

221 **3 Rotation of seismic anisotropy due to coseismic stress change.**

222 We now investigate the physical mechanism underlying this deep, persistent velocity
 223 change. Under a model of stress-induced seismic anisotropy, we hypothesize that if
 224 the earthquake induces a perturbation to the stress state in the fault zone, rotations in
 225 the stress field should, in turn, rotate the seismic fast-axis of anisotropy. Instead of stan-
 226 dardizing the receiver functions to eliminate backazimuth variability, we leverage this vari-
 227 ability to explore the evolution of seismic anisotropy in the crust. For each station, we
 228 group the receiver functions in a 180-day moving window, advancing in 10-day steps. We
 229 migrate the receiver functions from lag-time to depth using the direct converted phase
 230 moveout (Dueker & Sheehan, 1997). For each window, we stack the receiver functions
 231 in 10° backazimuth bins. For each depth-migrated and backazimuth-stacked receiver func-
 232 tion, we average the amplitudes in 1 km moving depth bins with a 0.1 km step, which
 233 further improves the stability of the amplitude variation in backazimuth and helps de-
 234 fine observational variance. We then perform a weighted least squares inversion of the
 235 the amplitude variation as a function of backazimuth for a set of backazimuth harmonic
 236 coefficients, along with a grid search over anisotropic fast-axis direction wherein the pre-
 237 ferred fast-axis direction is chosen to minimize a particular harmonic coefficient (Bianchi
 238 et al., 2010; Audet, 2015) (Fig. 3b-c). This process is performed independently for each
 239 depth and time window, allowing us to estimate the stability of the fast-axis direction
 240 over time. We quantify this stability by calculating the standard deviation of the fast
 241 axis σ_ϕ across all times before the 2019 Ridgecrest earthquake, and average the fast axes
 242 from depths where the $\sigma_\phi < 30^\circ$ for each station with at least 5 such depths that pro-
 243 duce stable ϕ estimates. The result is a time series of the azimuth of the anisotropic fast-
 244 axis over time (Fig. 3a). We then separately average the fast-axis orientations for one
 245 year prior to and following the 2019 Ridgecrest earthquakes, allowing us to estimate the
 246 coseismic rotation in fast-axis orientation (Fig. 3d) and map this coseismic reorienta-
 247 tion across the fault zone (Fig. 1a).

248 The background anisotropy is spatially coherent and reflects the dominant fault
 249 structures in the area, with a NW-SE trend along the Ridgecrest fault and rotating to
 250 a more E-W trend near the Garlock fault (Fig. 1a). Stations that do not pass the sta-
 251 bility criteria for a fast-axis estimate are spatially clustered, suggesting that random noise
 252 or seasonal variations dominate the recovered anisotropy. The coseismic rotation is also
 253 spatially coherent and decays with distance from the fault with a maximum of $|\Delta\phi| \approx$
 254 7° (Fig. 3d). This aligns well with estimates of the stress field rotation derived from ro-
 255 tation of focal mechanisms (Xu et al., 2020; S. Sheng & Meng, 2020), but did not rely
 256 on aftershocks from the M_w 6.4 to provide an estimate of the pre- M_w 7.1 stress state,
 257 and is thus more applicable to other large earthquakes without this doublet character-
 258 istic.

259 We also demonstrate that the coseismic rotation in anisotropy persists without re-
 260 covery, similar to the isotropic velocity change (Fig. 3a). This suggests that the evolu-
 261 tion of seismic anisotropy imaged here is different from the evolution and healing of damage-
 262 related anisotropy from shear wave splitting estimates of repeating earthquake phases
 263 (Jia et al., 2024). We suggest that this persistent rotation of seismic anisotropy reflects
 264 a coseismic rotation in the crustal stress field. This explains why the velocity change does
 265 not decay, since its recovery timescale would be associated with the long-term stress ac-
 266 cumulation of the inter-seismic phase of the earthquake cycle, rather than the short-term
 267 damage healing that dominates the post-seismic phase.

4 Conclusions

Our results demonstrate that the seismic cycle involves the entire crustal column, beyond just the brittle seismogenic zone. The lack of healing of these perturbations, together with the localization around the fault zone and rotation in seismic anisotropy, suggest that these observations capture dynamics beyond the damage that heals rapidly in the fault zone. We suggest that these observations capture the coseismic perturbations to the crustal stress field as it undergoes a constant evolution throughout the seismic cycle. This explains and is consistent with observations of evolving faulting style throughout the aftershock sequence (Trugman, 2020) and aligns well with the magnitude of focal-mechanism derived stress rotations (Xu et al., 2020; S. Sheng & Meng, 2020).

We also show that that the velocity change in the shallowest subsurface is not generally reflective of the evolution of fault zone material properties at seismogenic depths. This has implications for fault zone monitoring, as well as monitoring of other significant geohazards. For example, volcano monitoring would benefit from an ability to sense material property evolution in mid- and lower-crustal magma storage regions as a step toward understanding the processes that drive volcanic unrest and eruption. Subduction zone deformation is another interesting area for future work, where receiver function monitoring could reveal more about the processes driving slow fault slip (Gosselin et al., 2020) and megathrust rupture.

5 Materials and Methods

5.1 Receiver function calculation.

We select 31 broadband seismic stations within 120 km of the Ridgecrest earthquake. We primarily consider P-phase receiver functions using $M_w > 5.0$ earthquakes at teleseismic distance ($30^\circ - 100^\circ$) from 2015-2024, though we also consider PP-phase receiver functions at teleseismic distance ($90^\circ - 180^\circ$) from 2015-2024. We have 7017 P-phase receiver functions, 5500 of which pass quality control and are used for subsequent analyses. We calculate receiver functions using the Wiener deconvolution technique (Audet, 2010). We rotate the receiver functions in the P - S_V - S_H frame prior to deconvolution using the free-surface transfer matrix (Bostock, 1998). The receiver functions are then calculated as

$$R(\omega) = \frac{S(\omega)P^*(\omega)\Phi(\omega)}{|P(\omega)|^2}, \quad (1)$$

where ω is the angular frequency, $R(\omega)$ is the frequency-domain S_V or S_H receiver function, $P(\omega)$ is the frequency-domain P -component of the seismic data, $S(\omega)$ is the S_V or S_H component of the seismic data, and $\Phi(\omega)$ is a regularizing filter that essentially serves as a noise-adaptive, frequency-dependent water level. $\Phi(\omega)$ is given by

$$\Phi(\omega) = \frac{|P(\omega)|^2}{|P(\omega)|^2 + \frac{1}{4}|N_P(\omega)|^2 + \frac{1}{4}|N_S(\omega)|^2 + \frac{1}{2}|N_P^*(\omega)N_S(\omega)|}, \quad (2)$$

where $N_P(\omega)$ and $N_S(\omega)$ are the pre-event noise on the P - and S -components of the seismic data, respectively. The time-domain receiver function is found by inverse Fourier transformation of eqn.(1). To evaluate the quality of the receiver functions, we first evaluate its quality as a transfer function. We calculate

$$\bar{S}(\omega) = R(\omega)P(\omega), \quad (3)$$

i.e. the receiver function is the transfer function that maps the P -component of the seismic data to the S_V or S_H component of the seismic data. Because of the damping factor $\Phi(\omega)$, this is not a perfect reconstruction of $S(\omega)$. We then measure the correlation coefficient between the $S(\omega)$ and $\bar{S}(\omega)$ and remove any receiver functions with a reconstruction correlation coefficient less than 0.0. To prevent contamination from aftershocks,

311 we also enforce flatness in the preevent noise spectrum. To do this, we extracted two min-
 312 utes of seismic noise prior to the arrival of the teleseismic body waves used to construct
 313 the receiver functions. We calculate the power spectral density using the multitaper method
 314 (Prieto et al., 2009). We then resampled at 1/8th octave intervals and averaged over full
 315 octave ranges (McNamara & Buland, 2004). We then removed receiver functions with
 316 a preevent noise power 10 times the median absolute deviations above the median at fre-
 317 quencies above 2 Hz. This primarily removes aftershock-contaminated waveforms in the
 318 weeks following the 2019 Ridgecrest earthquake. The remaining receiver functions are
 319 bandpass filtered between 0.05 and 2 Hz. As an example, CI.WRC2 retains 7017 receiver
 320 functions after quality control, yielding an average event-rate of ~ 70 events/month.

321 5.2 Capturing waveform variations with optimal transport.

322 Seismic signals are characterized by both feature (amplitude) and structure (time-
 323 ordering) information. A fundamental operation of seismic velocity monitoring is to mea-
 324 sure temporal distortion by matching features across successive realizations of a seismic
 325 signal. We recast seismic signals as time-amplitude distributions and use optimal trans-
 326 port to define a distance between these distributions, provide a warping function that
 327 accommodates joint feature-structure changes, and provide a geometric structure to the
 328 space of waveform variations. We work within the Kantorovich formulation of optimal
 329 transport wherein we consider two density function $\mu(x)$ and $\nu(y)$ and a cost function
 330 $c : X \times Y \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ and search for a transport plan $\gamma(x, y)$ that is chosen such that

$$331 \quad \sum_{j=1}^N \gamma_{ij} = \mu_i; \quad (4)$$

$$332 \quad \sum_{i=1}^M \gamma_{ij} = \nu_j; \quad (5)$$

$$333 \quad \gamma_{ij} \geq 0, \quad (6)$$

334 where we have defined $\gamma_{ij} = \gamma(x_i, y_j)$, $\mu(x_i) = \mu_i$, and $\nu(y_j) = \nu_j$.

335 Based on ideas from (Trillos & Slepčev, 2016) and (Thorpe et al., 2017), (Métivier
 336 et al., 2018) propose to reimagine the seismic signal as a point cloud in time-amplitude
 337 space. That is, instead of applying optimal transport directly to the seismic signal $d(t)$,
 338 we consider the discrete graph given by the set of N points $\{(t_i, d_i) \in \mathbb{R}^2, i = 1, \dots, N\}$.
 339 This is accomplished by representing the signal as a sum of N Dirac delta functions in
 340 time-amplitude space (Métivier et al., 2018). We are then free to support a uniform dis-
 341 tribution on this point cloud. Formally, seismic signals d_1 and d_2 can be represented by

$$342 \quad \mu(t, d) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \delta(t - t_i) \delta(d - d_{1,i}), \quad (7)$$

$$343 \quad \nu(t, d) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \delta(t - t_i) \delta(d - d_{2,i}). \quad (8)$$

342 In this case, the optimal transport problem is a linear sum assignment problem, and the
 343 transport plan becomes a one-to-one map with no mass splitting with the optimal trans-
 344 port plan being known as the assignment matrix (Métivier et al., 2019). c_{ij} corresponds
 345 to the Euclidean distance between two points in time-amplitude space

$$346 \quad c_{ij}^\lambda = |t_i - t_j|^2 + \lambda^2 |d_1(t_i) - d_2(t_j)|^2, \quad (9)$$

347 where λ is a weighting parameter that controls the importance of transport in time vs.
 348 amplitude.

349 **5.3 Disentangling source and path variations with linear optimal trans-**
 350 **port.**

351 We now turn to the structure of the optimal transport space in order to disentangle
 352 independent modes of variation in the transport maps. To do this, we can rewrite
 353 the distance in the Monge formulation as a distance on the tangent space of a reference
 354 distribution μ_0 using the transport map f_i which minimizes eq. 3.6,

$$355 \quad d_{W_2}(\mu_0, \mu_i)^2 = \int_X |f_i(x) - x|^2 \mu_0(x) dx \quad (10)$$

$$356 \quad = \int_X |(f_i(x) - x) \sqrt{\mu_0(x)}|^2 dx \quad (11)$$

$$357 \quad = \int_X |\phi(\mu_i(x))|^2 dx \quad (12)$$

$$358 \quad = \|\phi(\mu_i(x))\|_2^2 \quad (13)$$

359 where we define the projection function

$$360 \quad \phi(\mu_i(x)) = (f_i(x) - x) \sqrt{\mu_0(x)} \quad (14)$$

361 which is a mapping from the manifold to the tangent space at μ_0 . Notice that the Wasser-
 362 stein distance becomes a common L^2 norm in the embedding space. Note also that $\phi(\mu_0) =$
 363 0 since $f_0(x) = x$, and that ϕ preserves distances to μ_0 , i.e. $\|\phi(\mu_i(x)) - \phi(\mu_0(x))\|_2 =$
 364 $\|\phi(\mu_i(x))\|_2 = d_{W_2}(\mu_0, \mu_i)$. The linear optimal transport distance is then defined as

$$365 \quad d_{LOT}(\mu_i, \mu_j; \mu_0) = \|\phi(\mu_i) - \phi(\mu_j)\|_2. \quad (15)$$

366 μ_i and μ_j are both embedded in the tangent space at a fixed reference μ_0 .

367 We can decompose each optimal transport map $f_i(x)$ into the identity and an op-
 368 timal displacement function $u_i(x) : X \rightarrow Y$,

$$369 \quad f_i(x) = x + u_i(x). \quad (16)$$

370 Given u_i for $i = 1, \dots, M$, our goal is to learn a subspace V for these displacement fields,
 371 where V has a basis v_j for $j = 1, \dots, K$. This allows us to write

$$372 \quad u_i(x) = \sum_{j=1}^K \alpha_j^i v_j(x). \quad (17)$$

373 We would like this basis to capture the independent modes of waveform variation due
 374 to changes in the geometry of the incident wavefield and changes in subsurface veloci-
 375 ties. We identify this problem of subspace modeling as a problem of blind source separa-
 376 tion, to which the independent component analysis method is well-suited. We turn
 377 to probabilistic principal component analysis (Tipping & Bishop, 1999) to reconstruct
 378 the missing data before using independent component analysis (Hyvärinen & Oja, 2000)
 379 to solve for the independent modes. We retain 50 principal components when reconstruct-
 380 ing missing data and perform ICA with 10 components.

381 The independent component analysis algorithm finds a basis of independent com-
 382 ponents (ICs) that can be linearly combined to reproduce the optimal displacement fields.
 383 That is, we assume that an ensemble of M optimal displacement maps $U = \{u_i \in \mathbb{R}^N, i =$
 384 $1, \dots, M\}$ can be generated via linear combination of a limited number L of sources. That
 385 is, we assume a decomposition of the form

$$386 \quad U \approx AS + N \quad (18)$$

387 where A is the $M \times L$ ‘‘mixing matrix,’’ S is the $L \times N$ source matrix, and N is an $M \times$
 388 N matrix containing Gaussian noise. Each row of S describes a source of waveform vari-
 389 ation, and is statistically independent from the other rows of S .

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5.4 Localizing velocity changes in depth

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To locate the velocity changes in depth, we invert the receiver functions for a 1D layered velocity structure that can explain the receiver function waveforms. We begin by stacking the receiver functions across all times, all slowness, and over the 220° – 250° backazimuth bin that contains the highest density of receiver functions. Our goal is not to produce a high quality seismic image of the subsurface, but rather to provide a rough association between lag-time in the receiver function and depth of the phase conversion or reverberation in the subsurface. We parameterize the Earth as a 1D layered velocity model, for the moment neglecting dipping structures and anisotropy. We consider depths down to 40 km and vary the number of layers from 10 to 30. We begin with the velocity model of (White et al., 2021) and extract a 1D column from the velocity model below each station. We enforce a constraint on the deep V_s to align with global velocity models. V_p/V_s is bounded below by $\sqrt{2}$ and bounded above by 2.5. We then calculate the receiver function through this velocity model using Telewavesim (Audet et al., 2019). We minimize the misfit and perform optimization using a sequential least squares programming algorithm (Kraft, 1988), which is a local (gradient-based) optimization method which is justified since the starting model is likely high quality given the extensive seismic imaging in the area. To estimate uncertainty in the resulting model, we apply perturbations to the initial velocity model, where the perturbations are drawn from a normal distribution with σ_α and σ_β given by the model in (White et al., 2021). We perform the optimization separately for each member of this ensemble, and show the resulting spread in the final velocity models. The number of layer is chosen by minimizing the Akaike Information Criterion corrected for use on small datasets

$$AICc = 2k - 2\ln(\hat{L}) + \frac{2k(k+1)}{n-k-1} \quad (19)$$

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where k is the number of model parameters, n is the number of data points, and \hat{L} is the maximum value of the likelihood function of the model. \hat{L} is evaluated as the maximum of the likelihood function for a gaussian distribution at the maximum likelihood estimators of the mean and the variance

$$\ln(\hat{L}) = -\frac{n}{2} (\ln(2\pi) + \ln(\sigma^2) + 1) \quad (20)$$

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where σ^2 is the unadjusted sample variance.

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With a velocity model that reproduces the receiver function, we apply perturbations to each layer of the velocity model to produce a set of perturbed receiver functions. We calculate the optimal transport maps between the reference receiver function and each of the perturbed receiver functions, providing a mapping between modeled velocity changes and the resulting waveform perturbations. For each perturbation depth, we calculate the optimal transport distance as a function of lag-time (Fig. 2b). We calculate the this time-depth perturbation map for each member of the ensemble of velocity models calculated above. we then average the optimal transport distances across the ensemble of models.

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5.5 Measuring coseismic deflection of seismic anisotropy

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1D layered media with no dipping layers or anisotropy should not result in any energy on the transverse component of the receiver function, i.e. P – S scattering at a discontinuity should only partition energy into S_V waves. These S_V waves should show no variation in backazimuth, though will display some minor variation in slowness. However, phase conversions generated at dipping discontinuities or in anisotropic media will produce both amplitude and travel-time variations. This results from perturbations in the scattering properties at layer boundaries as well as accumulated travel time changes by wave propagation through anisotropic media. These amplitude and travel time variations are characterized by periodic variations in backazimuth (Backus, 1965). These periodic variations in S_V and S_H differ by 90° (Bianchi et al., 2010). The backazimuth har-

437 monic decomposition technique decomposes these periodic amplitude variations into pe-
 438 riodic components $\sin(k(\theta - \phi))$ and $\cos(k(\theta - \phi))$, where θ is the backazimuth and ϕ
 439 is the symmetry axis of the source of the backazimuth variations, and is often equated
 440 with the direction of the fast-axis of anisotropy or the dip of a dipping layer. We con-
 441 sider $k \leq 2$.

442 We begin by migrating the receiver functions from lag-time to depth using the move-
 443 out for the Ps conversion calculated using 1D velocity profiles extracted below each sta-
 444 tion from a local 3D velocity model (White et al., 2021). This removes arrival time vari-
 445 ations due to small variations in slowness (Audet, 2015). We then stack the receiver func-
 446 tions in N backazimuth bins (we use 10° backazimuth bins). This results in a data ma-
 447 trix

$$\mathbf{d} = [S_{V_1}(z), \dots, S_{V_N}(z), S_{H_1}(z), \dots, S_{H_N}(z)]^T \quad (21)$$

448 We model the amplitudes as resulting from

$$\mathbf{m} = [A(z) \quad B_{\parallel}(z), \quad B_{\perp}(z), \quad C_{\parallel}(z), \quad C_{\perp}(z)]^T \quad (22)$$

449 which are related to the data matrix via the harmonics

$$\mathbf{G} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \cos(\theta_1 - \phi) & \sin(\theta_1 - \phi) & \cos(2(\theta_1 - \phi)) & \sin(2(\theta_1 - \phi)) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 1 & \cos(\theta_N - \phi) & \sin(\theta_N - \phi) & \cos(2(\theta_N - \phi)) & \sin(2(\theta_N - \phi)) \\ 0 & \cos(\theta_1 - \phi + \pi/2) & \sin(\theta_1 - \phi + \pi/2) & \cos(2(\theta_1 - \phi) + \pi/2) & \sin(2(\theta_1 - \phi) + \pi/2) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & \cos(\theta_N - \phi + \pi/2) & \sin(\theta_N - \phi + \pi/2) & \cos(2(\theta_N - \phi) + \pi/2) & \sin(2(\theta_N - \phi) + \pi/2) \end{bmatrix} \quad (23)$$

450 i.e.

$$\mathbf{d} = \mathbf{G}\mathbf{m}. \quad (24)$$

451 We solve for the harmonic coefficients through a weighted least squares inversion

$$\mathbf{m} = (\mathbf{G}^T \mathbf{W} \mathbf{G})^{-1} \mathbf{G}^T \mathbf{W} \mathbf{d} \quad (25)$$

452 where

$$\mathbf{W} = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{V_1}^{-2} & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_{V_2}^{-2} & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & \sigma_{V_N}^{-2} \\ \sigma_{H_1}^{-2} & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_{H_2}^{-2} & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & \sigma_{H_N}^{-2} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (26)$$

453 The symmetry axis ϕ is chosen by grid search to minimize the variance on the B_{\parallel} com-
 454 ponent in a given depth range. This is because when $\theta - \phi = 0$, there should be no
 455 splitting of the converted phase, i.e. there should be no SH-polarization and $B_{\parallel} = 0$.
 456 We estimate the variance in the linear model parameters by propagating the errors in
 457 the observations

$$\mathbf{C}_m = (\mathbf{G}^T \mathbf{W} \mathbf{G})^{-1} \quad (27)$$

458 which has the variance of the model parameters $\sigma_{m_i, WLS}^2$ on its diagonal. Since ϕ cor-
 459 responds to the direction that minimizes the variance of $B_{\parallel}(z)$ over some depth range,
 460 we propagate the uncertainty of B_{\parallel} into ϕ by taking the range of ϕ such that $\|B_{\parallel}(\phi) -$
 461 $B_{\parallel}(\phi^*)\|_2^2 \leq \sigma_{B_{\parallel}}^2$, where $\phi^* = \operatorname{argmin}_{\phi} (\|B_{\parallel}\|_2^2)$.

462 We perform this inversion of receiver function amplitudes for the harmonic coef-
 463 ficients and fast-axis of anisotropy in a 180-day moving window with 10-degree backaz-
 464 imuth stacks of depth-migrated receiver functions. To construct the data matrix \mathbf{d} , we
 465 first average the amplitudes in the moving depth window with a width of 1 km and a
 466 step of 0.1 km. The weights in the inversion are calculated from the data variances for
 467 each backazimuth bin over all times in the 180 day window and depths in the 1 km depth
 468 bin. We then invert the receiver function amplitudes for each time and depth bin sep-
 469 arately for the harmonic coefficients and fast-axis orientation. This produces a time-depth
 470 record of each harmonic component and the fast-axis orientation.

471 To reduce this into a single estimate of the anisotropy directions, we calculate the
 472 standard deviation of the resulting fast-axes, for each depth for all times before the 2019
 473 Ridgecrest earthquakes $\sigma_\phi(z)$. We then average the fast-axes through time for all depths
 474 where $\sigma_\phi(z) < 30^\circ$, and combine the uncertainties in quadrature. Larger thresholds in-
 475 clude more depths with poorly estimated anisotropy or unstable fast-axes, while lower
 476 thresholds would reduce the stability of the average fast-axis orientations. This results
 477 in a time series of the fast-axis orientation for each station (Fig. 3a). To estimate a sin-
 478 gle coseismic perturbation to the fast-axis direction, we average the fast-axis orientations
 479 over 1 year before the earthquake and 1 year after the earthquake (solid black lines in
 480 Fig. 3a). This results in a single estimate of the coseismic reorientation of the anisotropy
 481 for each station (Fig. 3d).

Figure 1. Signatures of damage and stress change deep beneath the Ridgecrest sequence. (a) Map of the Ridgecrest area with with broadband seismic stations shown as points colored by isotropic changes in seismic velocity measured at each station as well as the fast-axis direction of seismic anisotropy before (black) and after (colored by their angular perturbation) the Ridgecrest earthquake sequence. The inset shows the backazimuth distribution of receiver functions. (b) Decay of the velocity change with distance from the fault of M7.1 Ridgecrest event. (c) Receiver functions through time for station CI.WRC2. The black line marks the 2019 Ridgecrest earthquake sequence. Stacked receiver functions before (blue) and after (red) the earthquake are shown.

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Figure 2. Deep seismic velocity changes. (a) Receiver function waveforms before (blue) and after (red) the 2019 Ridgecrest earthquake after isolating the independent components that capture time-lapse velocity changes. (b) Optimal transport distances resolved in lag-time of the receiver function due to buried velocity changes at a range of depths. Two moveouts related to direct conversions and reverberated phases are highlighted. (c) Changes in seismic velocity (dv/v) time series for station CI.WRC2 resolved in six different bins corresponding to the colored boxes in (a).

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Figure 3. Imaging coseismic stress change with rotations in the seismic anisotropic fast-axis. (a) Time series of the direction of the fast-axis of seismic anisotropy for station CI.WRC2. Blue points are estimates of the fast-axis direction prior to the 2019 Ridgecrest earthquake, and red points use receiver functions only after the Ridgecrest earthquakes. The average fast-axis azimuth is shown for all times before and all times after the Ridgecrest earthquakes (dashed grey line) along with the average over one year before and after the earthquakes (solid black line). (b) Fit of the receiver function amplitudes as a function of backazimuth before (blue) and after (red) the Ridgecrest earthquake sequence at a common depth for the radial (b) and transverse (c) component of the receiver function. (d) Absolute coseismic perturbation to the fast-axis direction with distance from the fault, for both positive (green) and negative (orange) angular perturbations.

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